

(i)SDL Insight

Digital Lending pathways
in Italy, Poland and Spain

Report for Poland

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Abstract

The SDL Insight - Digital Lending pathways in Italy, Poland and Spain project, funded by Knowledge Rights 21 and coordinated by Deborah De Angelis, the Italian coordinator for KR21, aims to analyse digital lending (eLending), with a particular focus on (independent) Secure Digital Lending ((i)SDL) (defined below) in libraries across three European Union countries: Poland, Spain, and Italy. The project examines the factors and barriers that affect the full implementation of (i)SDL, serving as a starting point for developing strategies to overcome these challenges.

Participating in the project are the DDA Law Firm, CLAKP (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) of the IGSG (Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems)/CNR (National Research Council), the “Dario Nobili” Library of the Research Area of the National Research Council (CNR), the Library and Scientific Documentation Center of the CNR Research Area in Pisa for Italy, Centrum Cyfrowe for Poland, and Fesabid for Spain.

I. The Context

E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (published in May 2025). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features:

- 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case);
- 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book;
- 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model;
- 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming);
- 5) Lending is only for a limited period;
- 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book;
- 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive;
- 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

The partners of this research project are Italy: STUDIO LEGALE DDA; CLAKP (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) dell'IGSG (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari)/CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche), Poland: Centrum Cyfrowe and Spain: FESABID.

To enable libraries to implement the (i)SDL model, they must have two key rights: (1) the right to digitise paper books and (2) the right to lend them, including via e-Lending. Polish copyright law, specifically sec. 28(1)(2) and sec. 28(2), permits libraries to reproduce works in their collections for preservation or protection, without setting limits on the number of copies or the technology used—making this a potential legal basis for digitisation.

e-Lending of digitised books may then be justified under sec. 28(1)(1) combined with sec. 28(2), and the fact that the law does not prevent a dynamic interpretation aligned with the CJEU’s *VOB* ruling. This allows the concept of lending to include digital formats. According to Polish law (sec. 28(4)), Public Lending Right (PLR) remuneration applies to lending printed works created or published in Polish. If a book was originally published in print, both its paper and digital versions could be eligible for remuneration. However, in practice, PLR payments are generally only made for loans of physical books.

This legal framework led to Poland being classified in the second group of countries in the study *e-BOOKS AND SECURE DIGITAL LENDING IN EUROPEAN LIBRARIES. Comparative Analysis under National and International Law*¹. Countries in this group offer some possibility of interpreting existing national law in a way that allows for the implementation of e-Lending under the (i)SDL model—particularly by relying on the reasoning established in the *VOB* and *TU Darmstadt* judgments of the Court of Justice of the European Union.

II. Survey objectives

This survey is part of an initiative by Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) to collect insights from libraries in Spain, Italy, and Poland regarding (independent) Secure Digital Lending - (i)SDL. Its purpose is to identify, through input from professionals in the field, the barriers to implementing (i)SDL, including legal, technical, and operational challenges. Additionally, the survey aims to evaluate the sector’s level of understanding, knowledge, perceptions, and assumptions surrounding the topic, to help shape a more informed and effective response to this issue. The project outcomes could provide a foundation for future strategies to overcome these obstacles and support the mission of libraries in the digital realm.

III. The Questionnaire

A. Data and Methodology

A.1. Description of the questionnaire and of survey process

A.1.1. Questionnaire Population

The addressees of the questionnaire were Polish libraries of all kinds reached through professional Polish library associations and Centrum Cyfrowe’s professional network, in February and March 2025.

¹ Gliściński, K. (2025). *e-BOOKS AND SECURE DIGITAL LENDING IN EUROPEAN LIBRARIES. Comparative Analysis under National and International Law*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10960187>

As the survey was distributed directly by the library associations, we do not own the knowledge about the precise size of the population the survey was sent to. Centrum Cyfrowe itself shared the information to a newsletter contact base consisting of 2283 addresses (3944 emails sent total), and disseminated the survey on social media channels – Facebook (9800 followers) and LinkedIn (1500 followers). Overall, 86 libraries responded - for the reasons set out above it is not possible to calculate what response rate this represents.

A.1.2. Questionnaire Structure

The original survey was created in English by the project partners so that each of the three countries involved in the study followed the same data gathering structure. The ready questionnaire was then translated into Polish. It consists of 36 questions organized into 8 sections. Section I focuses on the profiles of the libraries and professionals responding. The remaining seven sections address various issues related to digital lending ((i)SDL), covering the following topics: Section II – digital lending; Section III – legal barriers; Section IV – technological and infrastructure barriers; Section V – risk of opposition; Section VI – human resources; Section VII – financial barriers; and Section VIII – other relevant issues.

Once the survey results were received, they were diligently analysed, and automatically translated back to English, allowing for conducting the analysis in English.

B. Results

B.1. Responses to Section I - THE PROFILE OF RESPONDING LIBRARIES

The majority of presented data (73%) comes from public libraries from different parts of Poland, representing both big and small cities, then from academic libraries (22%), and school libraries (2 %). Both Polish national libraries shared their insights as well. We also received data from a private digital library.

What type of library do you represent? (According to IFLA classification)

Around 55% of our respondents represent directors and senior management - lead officials - in different types of Polish libraries, while 35% of answers were submitted by different types of librarians with diverse experience and level of seniority. 8.5% of responses come from library technicians, defined as people responsible for delivering technical support to the library.

What is your role in the library?

Out of the 86 analysed libraries, most of them hold monographs - 77, serials - 31, and multimedia - 27. Surprisingly, only 13 reported having space for digital-only resources and 11 public domain content.

What types of collections does your library primarily hold?

How large is the physical collection of the library?

43% of respondents described the size of the physical collection of their library as very large, 40% as large, 14% as medium, and 2% as small. When looking at the answers related to the size of the digital collection in the library, the majority - 41% - described it as small, with only 14% describing this as very large and more than 22% unable to define the size of the library's digital collection. Amongst the potential conclusions that could be drawn from this, it is imaginable that these numbers show that the digitisation of books is still a process, with analogue book copies waiting to be digitised.

How large is the library's digital collection?

Moreover, almost 70% of responding libraries reported that there is no dedicated team in charge of digital services resources, making it possibly a challenge to introduce new digitally focused services such as (i)SDL.

Is there a dedicated team in the library dealing with digital services or resources?

B.2. Responses to Section II - DIGITAL LENDING

When it comes to specificities regarding e-lending service by Polish libraries, more than 60% of responding institutions currently do not offer e-lending services, mostly relying on analogue services. Most respondents coming from institutions that do offer digital services (61% of them) even then do not exactly know what digital lending

service is implemented - whether to the whole digital collection or to selected resources.

Does the library offer an e-lending service?

If yes, what e-lending model operates in the library?

Furthermore, the (i)SDL model is currently only being used very rarely, but there is an anticipation among a significant share of respondents that it will become more important in future..

Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

B.3. Responses to Section III - LEGAL BARRIERS

A great majority of the respondents stated that they do not have the knowledge to confirm whether the Polish copyright law or other legislation authorises (i)SDL. One of the rare respondents who could share an view stated:

The use of SDL (Secure Digital Lending) in Poland is permitted but must meet specific conditions in compliance with copyright law and regulations concerning the use of works for educational or other purposes, as well as the protection of intellectual property. In Poland, as in other European Union countries, copyright law governs the use of literary, scientific, artistic, and other works, including the rules for lending such works.

A few others referred to the importance of lending under the *one copy–one user* model, for a limited time.

Almost 35% of the respondents stated that Polish national regulations regarding (i)SDL were unclear, 45% responded “I do not know” to this issue. Both answers show how little knowledge there is on an organisational level regarding copyright and ethical issues.

How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

B.4. Responses to Section IV - TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

The majority of respondents marked all three factors: lack of adequate digitisation equipment, of an adequate archiving and digital rights management (DRM) systems, and of technical protection measures know-how as major barriers preventing them from advancing implementation of (i)SDL. Next to these they also flagged insufficient competences and skills in their respective teams linked to technology.

What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL? Each barrier rated on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0=I don't know, 1 = not a barrier and 5 = major barrier)

Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

B.5. Responses to Section V - RISK OF OPPOSITION

There is a lot of uncertainty to how the implementation of (i)SDL would be perceived by relevant stakeholders and the wider ecosystem. While almost 42% of respondents replied that there would be no resistance from within their institution to implementing the service, almost 50% were unable to clearly state what the approach in their organisations might be. This can be linked to the generally low level of knowledge about this type of e-lending, the institutional mindset, legal or technical concerns, and existing barriers.

Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or

In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

Additionally, 40% of respondents also stated that the publishing industry would be against the implementation of the (i)SDL model in Poland, making it an additional challenge for the introduction of the service.

How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

B.6. Responses To Section VI - HUMAN RESOURCES

When it comes to access to expert legal knowledge in libraries in Poland, only 23% of the respondents confirmed having access to a dedicated legal expert or adviser. The great majority cannot rely on such a service on a daily basis which potentially may impact institutional appetite for integration of new approaches and operational models which require access to legal expertise and intensive support in the implementation phase.

Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

As the (i)SDL model is barely recognised in Poland, there is, not surprisingly, very little training available to library professionals, unless the teams are really interested in it. Nevertheless, 73% of the respondents believe that such legal training and guidance would be necessary to be able to understand available options.

Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

A great majority of the respondents (64%) also flagged having no support from a technological expert who could analyse and lead the integration of the (i)SDL model into regular library operations. Additionally, no training on technological aspects of the approach has been offered so far to almost 60% of the respondents, with 70% of the respondents wishing to be trained on those aspects.

Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

In your opinion, is such training or technological guidance necessary?

B.7. Responses To Section VII - FINANCIAL BARRIERS

Furthermore, 64% respondents stressed having inadequate funding in their organisations to implement the (i)SDL model, which requires resources for digitisation, technical support and daily operations. Digitisation itself represents a great challenge for many questioned libraries.

Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i) SDL?

Are digitization tools and DRM systems affordable for your library?

B.8. Responses To Section VIII - OTHERS

While the existing level of knowledge on (i)SDL seems to be very limited, there is a visible appetite for learning more and participating in capacity building activities dedicated to the service.

Would you or your staff benefit from additional information or educational events regarding (i)SDL?

The expectation is that national policymakers facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries by first of all offering clarification on the use of (i)SDL, then supportive regulatory amendments establishing privileges for libraries allowing them to fulfil their public interest role in the digital ecosystem. Furthermore, training and capacity building for the sector should be designed and applied alongside with an awareness raising campaign. One respondent set out the following steps:

Clear legal regulations; no penalties for the unintentional sharing of a book for which permission was not obtained.

1. *A clear legal interpretation of what is allowed and what is not.*
2. *An open technical specification for the information/IT system enabling (i)SDL — outlining the required standards so that it can be developed using various tools, including existing systems.*
3. *A nationwide campaign targeting library directors and legal advisors — “Yes, you can do this!”*

Library experts who took part in the study are divided in terms of its vision of the potential of (i)SDL for future operations of the libraries. 40% do not know what the future holds - this might be linked to the general lack of knowledge of this legal solution. However, 53% believes (i)SDL will gain in importance. As one respondent stated:

Access to digital resources is the future, so I believe it is inevitable.

Due to the changing social landscape, e-services will be necessary to respond to the needs of local communities.

Especially in academic libraries, an increasing number of resources—particularly scholarly ones—are available only in digital form. Without appropriate legal frameworks, access to these types of resources will be limited.

(selection of answers to an open question in the iSDL survey)

Do you think (i)SDL will become more important for libraries in the future?

Some also confirm (38%) that there is already existing infrastructure in place that could be used to also operate the (i)SDL model in a secure way.

Could your library's (i)SDL system be integrated with existing catalogues and platforms?

There is no understanding whether (i) SDL allows for secure solutions in the libraries, with more than 45% stating "yes", almost 49% "not knowing" and almost 6% having concerns.

Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

Lastly, when it comes to discussing the negative consequences of not implementing (i)SDL in Poland, the questioned experts flagged blockages to the achievement of libraries' missions (the library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book) and loss of recognition and attractiveness in the dynamic emerging digital ecosystem (i.e. the library's services become less attractive compared to other libraries or digital platforms.)

What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

C. Summary of the results of the questionnaire

The results show relatively low knowledge and high uncertainty among the respondents in Poland about what the (i)SDL model entails, its specific characteristics, and its potential for implementation. The answers show discrepancies between Polish libraries - some (mostly from bigger cities and better funded) have broader relevant knowledge and are at a greater stage of maturity in the adaptation of operations to the digital world. Others speak about lack of resources (funding, skills, human resources) stopping them from focusing on digitisation and e-lending.

However, the appetite for testing new scenarios, like (i)SDL, is noticeable, as it facilitates or may facilitate additional access to knowledge for library users in Poland. The testing would nevertheless require provision of training for library experts, support in running dialogue between libraries and technology experts and clear regulatory guidelines from the state.

IV. Conclusions

Here are the main takeaways from the study:

1. Digitisation and e-lending is still a challenge for Polish libraries

While there is a sector of bigger libraries in Poland which champion digitisation and digital access, for the majority of smaller and local organisations this is still very challenging, mostly because of insufficient resources (both in terms of personnel and technical resources, such as scanners, servers, etc.) and skills. Only 36% of libraries questioned through the survey offer e-lending as a service. Respondents pointed out, among other things, the lack of an adequate (intuitive and simple) system to support digital lending. As one respondent set out:

We are a municipal library, we do not have digital collections, so I cannot answer some questions.

2. Little knowledge on e-lending models - need for awareness raising

There is very little knowledge in Polish libraries on (i)SDL in particular, and broader legal frameworks for their operation in general. Additionally there is too little discussion in the library sector on implementation mechanisms concerning e-lending models.

Only 29% of respondents believe it is very relevant to offer (i)SDL as a service. Around 70% of respondents wished to be trained on technological and legal features regarding (i)SDL to understand the concept better. Again, to share specific examples of respondents' views:

Unfortunately there is a lot of unclear information, in fact every lawyer has a different opinion about the possibilities and limitations of e-book lending.

Users are not aware of the (i)SDL model, but they often ask about the possibility of obtaining a digital version, especially of those items that we only provide on-site.

3. All kind of barriers are in place

There is no clear national guidance and interpretation on (i)SDL related regulations and the technical, economic and organisational means allowing for implementation of the (i)SDL e-lending model. This includes certainty on regulations allowing for (i)SDL and support for technological dialogue and acquisition of resources.

According to the respondents, an important barrier—alongside the general lack of knowledge about the legal basis for e-lending—is the absence of clear and specific regulations enabling a concrete form of e-lending. For the implementation of such a project, the availability of legal support for the e-lending process also appears essential, in order to minimise the legal risks associated with offering this type of service. One respondent recommended:

[the policy makers should] :

provide organizational support (clear regulations, organizational framework, sources and mechanisms of financing).

simplify procedures and support financing.

4. Appetite for (i)SDL potentially recognised

Although various barriers to the implementation of (i)SDL remain very much in place, and the general awareness level around the model is low among Polish librarians, 53% of respondents believe that the importance of (i)SDL will grow over time. This may translate into a growth in an appetite among libraries into testing the model, especially as it strengthens their position in their digital operational ecosystem and allows for modernisation and fulfilment of their public interest mission in the changing world. As one said:

(i)SDL has the potential that the traditional lending model cannot meet when it comes to the needs of a digitalising society.

Until the policy of most publishing houses changes regarding the purchase of institutional access to single e-books, the need for e-lending in the (i)SDL model will grow.

5. Call to facilitate cooperation

Access to knowledge, through exchange of best practices and discussion on challenges, as well as collaboration between libraries and service providers, needs to be supported in order to implement (i)SDL. Currently, libraries on their own do not have the in-house knowledge and resources to be able to address the topic alone. As one respondent set out:

[what the policy makers should do is to] Enable the use of know-how of entities that already have experience in implementing (i)SDL projects; facilitate networking and cooperation between public libraries and private entities in this area (in particular through the recommendation system); organize conferences and training for employees and directors of public libraries in the field of (i)SDL; implement legal assumptions and launch all necessary services comprehensively, as well as establish appropriate institutions to implement the amended and applicable regulations

Appendixes

Appendix A- Questionnaire

Questionnaire on the barriers to the adoption of (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL): Legal, technical, and operational challenges.

This questionnaire results from an initiative of [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21) aimed at gathering information from libraries in Italy, Poland, and Spain concerning (independent) **Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised by libraries where some protection measures are adopted to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limitate the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc. often named DRM Digital Rights Management Systems)²**. It investigates the legal, technical, and other barriers that influence the potential for further adoption of (i)SDL.

The partners of this research project are:

Italy: [STUDIO LEGALE DDA](#); [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) dell'IGSG (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari)/CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)

Poland: [CENTRUM CYFROWE](#)

Spain: [FESABID](#)

The project explores these issues to lay the groundwork for identifying the key challenges and potential benefits behind (i)SDL implementation. The project outcomes could provide a foundation for future strategies to overcome these obstacles and support the mission of libraries in the digital realm.

The questionnaire is divided into eight sections and contains **36 questions**.

Given the topic's relevance, please take about **20 minutes** to respond to the questionnaire we have prepared.

The deadline for completing the questionnaire is **February 26th, 2025**.

We greatly appreciate your participation in this survey, as your responses will directly contribute to shaping the future of (i)SDL in libraries across Europe.

² E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (scheduled for publication in January/February 2025). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features: 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case); 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book; 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model; 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming); 5) Lending is only for a limited period; 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book; 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive; 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

I. LIBRARY'S PROFILE

1. For which library are you responding to this questionnaire? (Add the library's name)

2. What is your role in the library?

3. What type of library are you answering for? Following [IFLA's typology](#):

- National
- Academic
- Public
- School
- Other

4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold?
(Select all that apply)

- Serials (e.g., journals, magazines, periodicals)
- Monographs (e.g., books, reports)
- Archival materials (e.g., manuscripts, historical documents)
- Multimedia (e.g., DVDs, audio recordings, images)
- Digital-only resources (e.g., e-books, databases, online journals)
- Public domain or out-of-copyright materials
- Other (please specify)_____

5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

- Yes

- No
- I don't know

II.DIGITAL LENDING

8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9. If you answer “yes” to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model.

- Digital lending provided for specific resources
- Digital lending fully provided
- I don't know

10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

11. If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- Public domain works
- In-copyright works which are out of commerce
- In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format
- In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

- Yes, there is high demand
- Yes, but the demand is moderate
- Very little demand
- No demand
- I don't know

Please specify your answer

13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

- Increase strongly

- Increase marginally
- Stay stable
- Decline
- I don't know

14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

- Essential
- Important but not essential
- Not important
- I don't know

Please explain why:

III. LEGAL BARRIERS

15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Not clear at all
- I don't know

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?

(Please rate each barrier on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0=I don't know, 1 = Not a barrier and 5 = Major barrier)

Barrier	0=I don't know	1 (Not a barrier)	2	3	4	5 (Major barrier)
Lack of adequate digitisation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of an adequate archiving system	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If you think there are other technological barriers, please indicate them below:

18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered Yes, please specify which consortium or collaboration

V. RISK OF OPPOSITION

19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please specify

20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)_____

21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)_____

22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

- Strongly supportive
- Neutral
- Opposed
- I don't know

VI. HUMAN RESOURCES

23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated legal staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary legal support

- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer "No" or "In progress" to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary technological support
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer "No" or "In progress" to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VII. FINANCIAL BARRIERS

29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VIII. OTHER

31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Please specify why

34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- The library loses its relationship with users
- The library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book.
- Users are less likely to engage with the library's services

- The library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options
- The library's services become less competitive than other libraries or digital platforms.
- There are none
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

Appendix B - Excerpt of the most significant free-text comments

(some of the comments are added directly in the text above)

What the policymakers should do:

First and foremost, it's essential to establish legal frameworks that ensure libraries do not feel anxious about implementation (i.e., fear of legal liability). In my opinion, libraries should be privileged institutions and subject to a different set of copyright laws.

Clear legal regulations; no penalties for the unintentional sharing of a book for which permission was not obtained.

- 4. A clear legal interpretation of what is allowed and what is not.*
- 5. An open technical specification for the information/IT system enabling (i)SDL — outlining the required standards so that it can be developed using various tools, including existing systems.*
- 6. A nationwide campaign targeting library directors and legal advisors — “Yes, you can do this!”*

To facilitate the implementation of (i)SDL in libraries, national policymakers should take a range of actions to ensure legal compliance, improve access to resources, provide financial support to libraries, and at the same time protect the rights of creators. Policymakers should also strive to maintain a balance between providing broad access to educational resources and ensuring appropriate protection of creators' rights and fair compensation.

On technological support:

It's hard to say — when we create a system, we build it functionally based on our own knowledge and ideas (or ones we've observed elsewhere). However, the actual implementation in the system is done by the developer. Ideally, we would have access to an IT-IP lawyer who could assess whether our ideas are legally sound or if something needs to be adjusted. At the moment, this responsibility falls on us — more specifically, voluntarily on me and officially on our in-house lawyer.

We did not plan for such services outside of our collaboration with the Library Deposit.